

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DYSLIPIDEMIA AND OBESITY AS RISK FACTORS IN CARDIAC ARRHYTHMIAS DIAGNOSED BY HOLTER MONITORING ECG OR STANDARD ECG

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Abstract

Introduction: In 2019, approximately 18 million persons died because of cardiac diseases, accounting for 5% were cardiac arrhythmias. Dyslipidemia and obesity are the major risk factors in cardiovascular pathologies. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), in 2016, 39% of people that are 18 years and older were overweight, obesity was identified in 13%. Body mass index can be divided in underweight, normal, overweight and obesity. Obesity can be subdivided in class 1, class 2, class 3 or severe obesity. Dyslipidemia can be hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia. The aim of this article is to assess the relation between dyslipidemia, obesity and cardiac arrhythmias.

Materials and methods: The study was effectuated by retrospective analysis of 94 histories from January 2022 to January 2023 in the Institute of Cardiology, the Republic of Moldova. In total, 94 patients were diagnosed with cardiac arrhythmias. Depending on the diagnostic method there were established two groups: Holter monitoring ECG (Group 1), standard ECG (Group 2).

Results: After effectuated analysis there were observed that in Group I hypercholesterolemia were in 65.75% of cases, hypertriglyceridemia in 17.81%, but in Group II hypercholesterolemia in 66.67% and hypertriglyceridemia in 4.10%. Depending on BMI in Group I the most frequent grade was overweight found in 49.32% of cases, mild obesity in 39.73%, moderate obesity in 5.48%, morbid obesity in 2.74% and within normal limits in 4.11%. In Group II the overweight was in 53.38%, mild obesity in 28.57%, moderate obesity 14.28% and morbid obesity in 4.76%, but BMI within normal limits was not identified in this group.

Conclusions: Hypercholesterolemia, overweight and obesity are very important risk factors in developing cardiac arrhythmias. Hypertriglyceridemia was encountered less often than other risk factors previously studied.

Keywords: cardiac arrhythmia, obesity, overweight, hypercholesterolemia, hypertriglyceridemia.

Introduction

A cardiac arrhythmia can be defined as an irregular heartbeat that often can be asymptomatic [3]. But there are some patients that can complain pre-syncope, syncope, dyspnoea, palpitations, chest pain and anxiety [2]. There are two main groups of cardiac arrhythmias like supraventricular and ventricular. Supraventricular arrhythmias are classified in sinus tachycardia, focal, multifocal and macroreentrant atrial tachycardia, atrial fibrillation, atrioventricular junctional tachycardia, atrioventricular reentrant tachycardia [1]. Ventricular arrhythmias are classified in ventricular tachycardia, premature ventricular contractions, torsades de pointes, ventricular flutter and fibrillation [11]. According to the WHO, the most frequent cause of global mortality, approximately 32%, are cardiovascular pathologies [5]. In 2017, in Republic of Moldova, the prevalence of atrial fibrillation was 3% in patients older than 20 years old [7].

Only in 2019 18 million people died because of heart diseases, in which cardiac arrhythmia were accounting for 5% [5]. In 2016, 39% of persons that are older than 18 years old were overweight, but obesity

was identified in 13% of cases [6]. Body mass index (BMI) is equal to the ratio between height (meters) and body mass (kilogramme). BMI can be classified in underweight range, overweight and obesity [4]. Also obesity can be divided into class 1, class 2 and class 3 or morbid obesity [4]. Classification of dyslipidemia is based on two types of the imbalance of lipids and there are hypercholesterolemia, that can be prevailed by low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL cholesterol) or high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and another type is hypertriglyceridemia [8].

Aim of the study

Taking in the consideration that dyslipidemia and excessive weight are the major risk factors of cardiovascular diseases, the objective of the study is to assess the relation between obesity, dyslipidemia and cardiac arrhythmias. Also we considered that it was necessary to find out the relation between gender and dyslipidemia, excessive weight and cardiac arrhythmias.

Materials and methods

This study is based on retrospective analysis of 94 patient's medical records from January 2022 to January

2023 in the Institute of Cardiology, the Republic of Moldova. From 1589 patients hospitalized in the general cardiology department, we selected 94 patients based on the inclusion criteria: the diagnosis of cardiac arrhythmia, age more than 18 years. Patients without cardiac arrhythmias and age younger than 18 years were excluded. Group I are patients with cardiac arrhythmias confirmed by Holter monitoring ECG. Group II are patients with cardiac arrhythmias confirmed by ECG standard.

The classification of BMI is:

- 1) Underweight – <18 kg/m²
- 2) Normal – 18.5-24.9 kg/m²
- 3) Overweight – 25.0-29.9 kg/m²
- 4) Obesity – >30.0 kg/m²
 - Class I – 30.0-34.9 kg/m²
 - Class II – 35.0-39.9 kg/m²
 - Class III – >40 kg/m²

All patients' personal information remains confidential.

The obtained descriptive statistical results have been introduced in Microsoft Office Excel and Microsoft Office Word with charts and diagrams.

Results

The study analysed 94 patients with cardiac arrhythmias confirmed by Holter monitoring ECG or ECG standard.

Figure 1 shows the gender distribution of patients with cardiac arrhythmias, confirmed by Holter monitoring ECG or standard ECG. In both groups of effectuated study dominated male gender. In Group I, where cardiac arrhythmias were confirmed by Holter monitoring ECG, men were 53.42% and women in 46.58% of cases. But in Group II, where cardiac arrhythmias were confirmed by standard ECG, men were in 52.38% of cases and women in 47.62%.

Figure 1. Patients' distribution according to gender.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of patients with cardiac arrhythmias according to the classification of obesity by BMI.

Figure 2. Patients' distribution according to BMI classification.

Normal weight was observed in Group I 4.11%, but in Group II 0%. In Group I overweight was

identified in 49.32% and Group II in 53.38%. Obesity class I was in Group I in 39.73% of cases and in Group

II in 28.57%. In Group I 39.73% and in Group II 28.57% had obesity class II. The severe obesity was identified more in Group II 4.76% and less in Group I 2.74%.

Figure 3 demonstrates the distribution of patients with cardiac arrhythmias according to dyslipidemia.

Figure 3. Patients' distribution according to types of dyslipidemia.

Hypercholesterolemia prevailed by LDL cholesterol, was observed in both groups. In Group I, where cardiac arrhythmias were diagnosed by Holter monitoring ECG, in 65.75% of cases and in Group II, where cardiac arrhythmias were diagnosed by ECG standard, in 66.67%. Hypertriglyceridemia was found in Group I in 17.81% of cases and in Group II of the study in only 9.52% of cases.

Discussions

In the study from 94 patients 53.19% were male gender and 46.81% female. These results match with results from a study from Nepal where male gender in 52.2% of cases and female gender prevailed in 47.8% of cases [43]. Normal weight was met in only 3.19% of cases from all patients, overweight and obesity were met in 96.81% of 94 patients. The meta-analysis, that included 51 studies and 600 000 patients determined the impact of overweight and obesity on atrial fibrillation [9]. The result was that incident of atrial fibrillation was increasing with 20-30% with every 5 point elevating in BMI [9]. In our study we demonstrated that from 94 patients 65.96% had hypercholesterolemia prevailed by low-density lipoprotein cholesterol and 15.96% had hypertriglyceridemia. In Helsinki was effectuated a study where participated 725 patients with cardiac arrhythmias [10]. In that study was observed that in 41.6% of cases was found hypercholesterolemia prevailed by LDL cholesterol and 22.1% was found hypertriglyceridemia [10].

Conclusions

1. Cardiac arrhythmias were observed more frequent in male gender – in 53.19% of cases.
2. Overweight and obesity were observed in 96.1% of patients with cardiac arrhythmias.
3. Hypercholesterolemia was found in 65.96% of cases and hypertriglyceridemia in 15.96% of cases.

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